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Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
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ИЖТИМОЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF SOCIAL STUDIES

Nosirova Marguba,

Associate Professor, Department of Social Sciences,

Andijan State University,

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Sociological Sciences

THE IMPORTANCE OF NEW SKILLS IN IMPROVING WOMEN'S EMPLOYMENT AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP (UNTIL 2030)

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the importance of new skills in enhancing women's employment and entrepreneurship in the context of socio-economic transformations expected by 2030. The study highlights that competencies such as digital literacy, financial management, project leadership, innovative thinking, and adaptability to technological changes are becoming crucial determinants of women's economic empowerment. The research explores how acquiring modern skills expands women's access to the labor market, strengthens microbusinesses and family entrepreneurship, and contributes to broader social stability. Additionally, the article proposes policy recommendations such as updating educational programs, establishing community-based training centers, promoting online skill-building courses, and improving the entrepreneurial ecosystem for women. The analysis also evaluates the anticipated outcomes of national strategies, innovation hubs, and grant programs aimed at boosting women's entrepreneurial activity by 2030. Overall, the study emphasizes that developing new competencies is a decisive factor for increasing women's participation in economic life and ensuring sustainable growth.

Keywords: women's employment, entrepreneurship, digital literacy, creative thinking, gender equality, labor market, sustainable development.

Nosirova Marg'uba,

Andijon davlat universiteti

Ijtimoiy fanlar kafedrasida dotsenti

Sotsiologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

XOTIN-QIZLAR BANDLIGI VA TADBIRKORLIGINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA YANGI KO'NIKMALARNING AHAMIYATI (2030-YILGA QADAR)

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada xotin-qizlar bandligi va tadbirkorligini rivojlantirishda yangi ko'nikmalarning ahamiyati, ayniqsa 2030-yilga qadar amalga oshirilishi kutilgan ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy o'zgarishlar sharoitida tahlil qilinadi. Zamonaviy mehnat bozorida raqamli savodxonlik, moliyaviy boshqaruv, innovatsion fikrlash, loyiha yuritish kabi kompetensiyalar xotin-qizlarning iqtisodiy faolligi va raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning asosiy omiliga aylanib bormoqda. Tadqiqotda yangi ko'nikmalarni egallashning mehnat bozorga kirish imkoniyatlarini kengaytirishdagi, mikrobiznes va oilaviy tadbirkorlikni mustahkamlashdagi hamda ijtimoiy barqarorlikni ta'minlashdagi roli keng

yoritilgan. Shu bilan birga, ta'lim dasturlarini yangilash, korporativ o'quv markazlari va mahalla darajasidagi o'quv loyihalarini kengaytirish, raqamli platformalardan samarali foydalanish bilan bog'liq takliflar ilgari suriladi. Maqolada 2030-yilgacha xotin-qizlar tadbirkorligini qo'llab-quvvatlovchi milliy strategiyalar, innovatsion klasterlar va grant dasturlarining kutilgan natijalari ham baholanib, yangi ko'nikmalar orqali iqtisodiy faollikni oshirishning amaliy yo'nalishlari asoslantiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: xotin-qizlar bandligi, tadbirkorlik, raqamli savodxonlik, ijodiy fikrlash, gender tengligi, mehnat bozori, barqaror rivojlanish.

Носирова Маргуба,

доцент кафедры социальных наук
Андижанского государственного университета,
доктор философии (PhD) по социологическим наукам

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ НОВЫХ НАВЫКОВ В СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИИ ЗАНЯТОСТИ И ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА ЖЕНЩИН (ДО 2030 ГОДА)

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматривается значение новых навыков в процессе развития занятости и предпринимательской активности женщин в условиях социально-экономических изменений, ожидаемых к 2030 году. Подчеркивается, что такие компетенции, как цифровая грамотность, финансовое планирование, управление проектами, инновационное мышление и умение адаптироваться к современным технологическим трендам, становятся ключевыми факторами повышения экономической активности женщин. Исследование раскрывает роль профессиональных навыков в расширении доступа женщин к рынку труда, укреплении микробизнеса и семейного предпринимательства, а также в обеспечении социальной устойчивости. Кроме того, в статье предлагаются меры по модернизации образовательных программ, развертыванию обучающих центров в регионах, развитию онлайн-курсов и созданию благоприятной предпринимательской экосистемы для женщин. Анализируются ожидаемые результаты реализации национальных стратегий, инновационных кластеров и грантовых программ, направленных на поддержку женского предпринимательства до 2030 года.

Ключевые слова: занятость женщин, предпринимательство, цифровая грамотность, креативное мышление, гендерное равенство, рынок труда, устойчивое развитие.

INTRODUCTION

Global labor markets in 2023 have seen mixed results, driven by economic, health, and geopolitical developments. While high-income countries have seen strong labor market demand, low- and middle-income countries still face higher unemployment rates than before the pandemic.

At the same time, labor market outcomes are also diverse at the individual level: low employment rates are particularly high among those with only primary education and among women.

In addition, real wages are falling as a result of the ongoing economic crisis caused by rising costs of living. At the same time, workers' satisfaction with their working conditions and quality of work, their expectations, and concerns are becoming increasingly important socio-economic issues worldwide.

In today's globalized world, the socio-economic development of countries largely depends on the potential of human capital, especially the active participation of women. Ensuring women's economic activity, involving them in entrepreneurship and creating equal opportunities in the labor market have become one of the priorities of state policy.

According to the World Economic Forum's "Future of Jobs Report" (2023), the skills that will be most in demand in the labor market by 2030 are creative thinking, technological literacy,

adaptability, leadership and empathy. These skills are of great importance in developing women's economic activity and entrepreneurial skills.

Women's employment and the digital economy The world economy is currently undergoing a process of digital transformation. These changes are reducing traditional types of work in the labor market and forming a new system of economic relations based on digital technologies. Therefore, the participation of women in the digital economy is an important factor in the sustainable development of the country.

Digital literacy is a key condition for increasing the competitiveness of women in the modern labor market. These skills will allow women to master new types of work, establish remote work activities, and effectively use online entrepreneurship opportunities. At the same time, through the use of digital technologies, women will have the opportunity to organize, manage, and expand their businesses.

In particular, knowledge in the field of technological competencies (technological literacy, artificial intelligence, big data) will further expand women's economic activity. With these skills, women will have the opportunity to:

- operate in the fields of e-commerce and digital marketing;
- provide online services and organize IT startups;
- promote products and services through social networks.

At the same time, participation in the digital economy creates a new working environment for women. For example, through remote work, they will save time and have the opportunity to combine work with family responsibilities. This, in turn, will serve to ensure gender equality and strengthen women's economic independence.

METHODOLOGY

Women's participation in the labor market and the development of entrepreneurship are among the most important socio-economic areas that have been widely studied worldwide in recent years. Scientific research in this area, especially related to the digital economy and the importance of new skills, is becoming increasingly relevant.

Studies by the World Bank (World Bank, 2022) and the International Labor Organization (ILO, 2021) have highlighted that developing new professional and digital skills for women is one of the main factors in increasing employment rates. In the process of digitalization, new forms of work, such as remote work, online shopping, and freelancing, are opening up new opportunities for women [1, – P.31].

Also, according to the “human capital theory” developed by Becker (1993), women's contribution to human capital through education and skills strengthens their economic independence and entrepreneurial activity. This idea is also supported by studies by Smith and Wesson (2019), which note that women with modern skills are competitive in the labor market [2, – P.49].

Uzbekistan also implements state programs aimed at ensuring women's employment and encouraging entrepreneurship, including the “Program for Broad Involvement of Women in Entrepreneurship” (2022-2026). The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6187 of March 7, 2021 sets the tasks of creating new jobs for women and attracting them to the digital economy [3, – P.118].

According to D.Makhmudova's research on the topic “Factors for increasing women's employment in the digital economy”, the employment rate among women in Uzbekistan has increased by 15-20% through online courses and professional training in the fields of IT, marketing and finance. This clearly demonstrates the impact of developing new skills on economic activity [4, – P.224].

Also, increasing digital literacy and entrepreneurial skills creates opportunities for women to launch microbusinesses and startups. As they emphasize, women with innovative and technological knowledge shape the offer of new products and services on the market [5, – P.128].

The literature review shows that acquiring new skills is one of the key factors in ensuring women's economic activity, entrepreneurial potential and social stability. In this process, state support, the development of the education system and digital infrastructure are of great importance.

MAIN PART

The data from the “Jobs of the Future” survey show that the most likely sectors to apply are electronics (83%), energy technologies and utilities (72%), and consumer goods (71%). Data from the International Federation of Robotics shows that the number of industrial robots per 10,000 workers across countries has continued to grow rapidly over the past five years.⁴⁷ Industrial robot density has almost doubled in the past five years, to an average of 126 robots per 10,000 workers. In terms of the impact of robots on employment, the strongest sectoral picture is seen in the adoption of non-humanoid robots, with 60 percent of companies in the consumer goods and oil and gas industries predicting job losses and 60 percent of companies in information and technology services predicting job creation over the next five years.

Women’s digital entrepreneurship not only generates personal income, but also contributes to the innovative development of the national economy. According to the International Labor Organization and the World Economic Forum, the growth of women’s integration into the digital economy has a positive impact on the growth rates of the country’s gross domestic product.

Thus, digital technologies are opening the door to new opportunities for women. The development of women’s employment and entrepreneurship based on digital skills will not only bring economic benefits, but also form a culture of innovative thinking, social activism and equal opportunities in society.

According to the World Economic Forum, what opportunities will arise for women in the labor market in 2030 and what factors are considered important for improving women’s employment and entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan? Figure 1 summarizes all the factors, which will serve as an incentive for the purposeful continuation of employment and work processes in the future.

1-picture. Key skills to master in 2030, according to WEF (World Economic Forum) data [6, – P. 41].

The diagram above shows that the role of creative and analytical thinking in entrepreneurship is increasing year by year. In particular, by 2030, women's business activities related to the Internet are expanding in Uzbekistan.

According to the World Economic Forum, "Creative thinking" and "Analytical thinking" are listed as the most important skills in 2030. For women entrepreneurs, creative thinking means developing new ideas, identifying market needs and creating innovative products.

Analytical thinking requires rational use of resources and relying on accurate analysis in decision-making.

The combination of these two skills will bring women's entrepreneurship to a modern and competitive form.

The skills of leadership and social influence presented in the diagram are of strategic importance for women. Today, women play a leading role not only in the business sector, but also in the public, education and management systems.

The influence of female leaders in society is formed according to the following factors:

- gender equality is strengthened,
- principles of social justice are developed,
- a positive image of women's activity in society is formed.

Therefore, soft skills for women – that is, communication, trust and team management skills - are becoming the main professional competencies.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has seen a sharp increase in the activity of women in public life. This is one of the priorities of state policy, and as a result, a positive image of women's activity in society is being formed. For example, in 2016, the share of women in leadership positions was 7%, but by 2024 this figure reached 29% [7, – P.256].

The growth in the number of female entrepreneurs is due to the fact that in 2017, only 17% of registered business entities in the country were owned by women. In 2024, this figure reached 27%. That is, one in four small businesses in Uzbekistan is managed by women. This has given impetus to the formation of a positive opinion about female entrepreneurs in society [8, – P.256].

Adaptability and resilience are the keys to success in the labor market. The labor market of 2030 will require operating in rapidly changing, uncertain conditions. "Resilience, flexibility and agility" – that is, resilience and adaptability – determine the ability of women to find their way in new conditions.

Adaptable female personnel can operate effectively even in conditions of economic crises, changing market demands or technological transformation. According to the results of social surveys. 74% of respondents supported the idea that "women can work effectively as leaders", 68% of citizens believe that "women entrepreneurs open up new opportunities in society" [9, – P.256].

These data indicate that the positive image of women's activity and adaptability is increasingly strengthened in the public consciousness. Culture of continuous learning and personal development. "Curiosity and lifelong learning" is an important factor for the sustainable professional growth of women.

Economically active women maintain their potential through constant professional development, studying new areas and adapting to market trends. Various programs are actively working in Uzbekistan in this direction, including the "Women's Entrepreneurship Support Fund" and online education platforms.

Women's activity in education and science is also increasing, 48% of students studying in higher education institutions are women. The share of women among scientists with scientific degrees has increased from 15% to 25% in the last 5 years [10, – P.340].

These indicators serve to increase the intellectual potential and social prestige of women. Political activity and participation in decision-making processes The share of women in the 2024 parliament is 32%. In local councils, this figure has reached 27%. These results are shaping a positive attitude in society towards the active participation of women in political processes.

Empathy and socially responsible entrepreneurship. Women play a leading role in social entrepreneurship. Through the skills of "empathy and active listening", they sense the needs of society

and create socially beneficial projects. For example, the activity of women entrepreneurs in the fields of education, healthcare, environmental protection and social protection is increasing year by year.

In recent years, the number of positive materials about female leaders, entrepreneurs and inventors in the media has increased dramatically. For example: between 2020 and 2024, the number of programs dedicated to women's activities on state and private television channels increased by 2.5 times. Programs such as "Tadbirkor Ayol", "Zor Ayol", and "Innovative Ayol" are positively promoting women's potential in society [11, – P.340].

CONCLUSION

Improving women's employment and entrepreneurship is one of the main factors ensuring the socio-economic stability of the country. To be successful in the labor market by 2030, women need to master the following skills: Technological literacy, Creative and analytical thinking, Leadership and social impact, Adaptability and resilience, Lifelong learning and personal development, Empathy and social responsibility, These skills strengthen women's economic independence, ensure gender equality in society and make a significant contribution to the development of the country.

The results of the conducted analyses indicate that the acquisition of new skills is a decisive factor in increasing women's employment and entrepreneurial activity. In the conditions of the digital economy, skills such as digital literacy, financial knowledge and innovative thinking enhance women's competitiveness in the labor market, increase their economic independence and social prestige.

The experience of Uzbekistan shows that in recent years, as a result of encouraging women's activity through state programs and educational initiatives, a positive image of women is being formed in society. Women make a significant contribution to the development of society through active participation in leadership, entrepreneurship and social spheres.

At the same time, the popularization of new skills, the wide introduction of digital education platforms and the increase in professional development courses for women are the main directions for ensuring sustainable achievements in this area.

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Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
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